

МУСТАҚИЛЛИК ЁИЛЛАРИДА ЎЗБЕК ВА ҚИРҒИЗ АДАБИЁТШУНОСЛИК ТЕРМИНЛАРИ ТАКОМИЛИ

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Аннотация: Мустақиллик даврида ўзбек адабиётшунослиги терминологиясини ўрганишга оид бир қатор тадқиқотлар амалга оширилди. Эътиборли томони шундаки, мустақиллик даврида фаннинг барча соҳаларида бўлгани каби адабиётшунослик соҳасида ҳам ўзгаришлар содир бўлди, воқелик фактларини тасвирлашда миллийлик нуқтаи назаридан ёндашишга интилиш кучайди. Ушбу мақоламизда ўзбек ва қирғиз адабиётшунослик терминларининг мустақиллик давридаги тараққиётига доир масалаларга тўхталиб ўтдик.

Калит сўзлар: термин, маросим фольклори, нақл жанри, ўзбек ва қирғиз фольклори, типологик ўхшашлик, қофия, ички қофия, бошқофия, зулқофиятайн, радиф, ҳожиб.

Аннотация: В период независимости был проведен ряд исследований по изучению терминологии узбекской литературоведческой критики. Примечательно, что за период независимости, как и во всех сферах науки, произошли изменения в области литературоведения, усилилось стремление подходить с национальной точки зрения при описании своих реалий. В этой статье мы затронули вопросы, связанные с развитием узбекских и киргизских литературных терминов в период независимости.

Ключевые слова: обрядовый фольклор, жанр повествования, узбекский и киргизский фольклор, типологическое сходство, рифма, внутренняя рифма, главная рифма, зулқофиятайн, радиф, ҳожиб

Annotation: During the period of independence, a number of studies were conducted to study the terminology of Uzbek literary criticism. It is noteworthy that during the period of independence, as in all spheres of science, there were changes in the field of literary studies, the desire to

approach from a national point of view when describing their realities increased. In this article, we touched upon issues related to the development of Uzbek and Kyrgyz literary terms during the period of independence.

Keywords: *ceremonial folklore, narration genre, Uzbek and Kyrgyz folklore, typological similarity, rhyme, inner rhyme, head rhyme, zulqofiyatayn, radif, hajib.*

During this period, a significant part of the research related to the terms of literary criticism is devoted to the genres of oral creativity of the people. Халқ оғзаки ижодига оид терминлар Маматқул Жўраевнинг «Ўзбек мавсумий маросим фольклори» (2008), «Фольклоршунослик асослари» (2009), Асқар Мусақулов «Ўзбек халқ лирикаси»(2010), Абдуолим Эргашев «Қашқадарё-Сурхондарё дostonчилиги» (2008), Жаббор Эшонқул «Ўзбек фольклорида туш ва унинг бадиий талқини» (2011), Шомирза Турдимов «Гўрўғли» дostonларининг генезиси ва тадрижий босқичлари» (2011), Адҳамжон Ашуров «Ўзбек халқининг қадимий эътиқод ва маросимлари»(2007) асарларида илмий жиҳатдан асослаб берилди Some authors, who based scientifically, such as Mamatqul Juraev's work, " Uzbek seasonal ritual folklore " (2008), "Basics of folklore" (2009), Askar MUSAQULOV's work, "Uzbek folk lyrics"(2010), Abdulolim Ergashev's work, "Kashkadarya-Surkhandarya epic" (2008), Jabbor Eshonkul "A dream in Uzbek folklore and its artistic interpretation" (2011), Shomirza Turdimov's, "Gurugli" (it means in English , the son of grave) genesis and stages of epic development" (2011), Adhamjon Ashurov's work, "Ancient beliefs and rituals of the Uzbek people"(2007). In addition, many genres of folk oral art have been studied in monographic terms. In particular, issues related to the historical roots and artistic interpretation of the image of a tarlon (horse) in Uzbek folk tales, the interpretation of time and space in Uzbek fairy tales, the image of Tarlon in Uzbek folklore, the motif of sleep in Uzbek folklore and its artistic interpretations, literary terms in works dedicated to the genre of transport in Uzbek. In the study of M. Temirova of proverbs in Uzbek and Kyrgyz folklore, the role of this term in literary studies, the belonging of Uzbek and Kyrgyz folk proverbs to each other in the context of common Turkic folklore, by checking the history of the creation of proverbs and the foundations of their formation, the definition of common and various aspects, checking stages, highlights the structural and poetic typology of Uzbek and Kyrgyz folk proverbs [1]. The

significance of the research lies in the fact that they summarize Uzbek and Kyrgyz folk proverbs, compare their mutual typological similarity, diversity of topics, the problem of artistry, and opinions are based on the latest achievements of folklore. Therefore, this work can be considered as one of the achievements in the field of terminology of literature in the Turkic languages. Among these researches the work carried out by D.Khotamova stands out. Dictionaries [2] and articles created by the scholar cover the current state of literary terms and the problems of alternatives. A.Asallaev, V.Rakhmonov, F.Musurmonkulov's dictionary "Charm of Fine Arts" for school education provides information on a number of arts used in Uzbek literature. The dictionary consists of three parts, the first of which is called "Ma'naviy sant'atlar" (Spiritual Arts). This section provides information about the art of tashbeh, ukhshatish san'ati (analogy), istiora, sinekdokha, tafrit, mubolaga (exaggeration), tashkhis, intoq, irsoli masal, tazod, talmeh, tajnis, tanosub, tajohuli orifona, ruju, husni talil, iyhom, laf and nashr, tazmin, sifatlash. The second part is called "Lafziy sanat" (word art), in this section rhyme, inner rhyme, head rhyme, zulqofiyatayn, radif, hajib, takrir, mukarrar, tardi aks, tadid, ishtiyoq, kaytarik, tasbe, tasdir, iltifot, tarse, nido, saj. The "Harfiy sanat" (letters arts) section provides examples of such types of art as kitobat, istikhroj, muammo, muvashshah, tavzi, kalb [3].

The period of independence in Uzbek literature D.Kuronov, Z.Mamajonov, M. The creation of the Sheralieva Dictionary of Literary Studies was one of the great achievements in this field. Compiled in the form of a dictionary, this book shows the content, genesis, language, genre and genre of terms used in Uzbek literature. The "Short Dictionary of Folklore Terms" prepared by S. Ruzimbaev and H. Ruzmetov in Uzbek literature also enriched the terminology of literary criticism with new information. Significantly, although the booklet is compact in size, it not only explains the literary terms used in folklore genres, but also contains information about the life and work of well-known folklorists, bakhshis, khalfas.

Changes in the field of Uzbek literature during the period of independence, in particular in terminology, were reflected in Kyrgyz literature. In the 1990s, even in Kyrgyz literary studies, drastic changes took place. The research conducted in the Kyrgyz literature began to highlight issues related to the origin of the Kyrgyz people, their historical and cultural ties with other peoples, the oral creativity of the people. In this regard, it should be noted that the epic "Manas", an example of the national values of the Kyrgyz people, the spiritual heritage that has been formed for

centuries, is a source for many scientific studies. The epic "Manas" is a valuable source not only for the folklore of the Turkic peoples, but also for such sciences as linguistics, terminology, history, ethnography. Research on the development of Kyrgyz terminology by Chingiz Kadyrova on the terminology of military words based on the epic "Manas" [4], G.K. Abdikadirova dedicated PhD dissertation was made as a worthy contribution. During this period, J. Sheriev and A. Muratov co-authored a textbook "Literature: Terminology's Explanatory Dictionary" [7] and M. Borbugulov's "Literary Theory: Textbook". [8]. In addition, a number of works devoted to the study of general issues of literary terms, the peculiarities of the use of individual literary terms in literary texts. The book "Introduction to Manas Studies" by T.A Bakchiev for university students also contains explanations of some literary terms. [9].

We can continue to give more such examples, ideas. Summarizing the above, it becomes clear that there are common sides inherent in the Uzbek and Kyrgyz peoples. Like many Turkic peoples, Uzbek and Kyrgyz peoples have lived side by side for centuries. The emergence of socio-cultural ties between them dates back to distant times. The connection between these two peoples has formed a community and commonality in their spiritual values, traditions, rituals and traditions, their customs and worldview, their art and culture, and fiction. Therefore, literature, which is a product of the artistic creativity of these peoples, cannot be studied without a clear understanding of their centuries-old history. Various socio-political events in history, changes in the environment have also made certain differences in the literary studies of the Uzbek and Kyrgyz peoples. Therefore, at a time when the Turkic peoples have gained independence today, realized their national identity, became interested in studying national and spiritual values, the history of literature, a comparative analysis of the terms of literary studies of the Uzbek and Kyrgyz peoples will undoubtedly contribute to further strengthening the cultural, scientific and literary ties between them.

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